

FORMATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL COMPETENCE AMONG STUDENTS

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Annotation. The structure and content of the model of the process of formation and development of environmental competence of future teachers will be considered. As a result of the research, the following main directions of the formation and development of environmental competence have been identified: retraining and professional development, methodological and information support, creation and support of a digital-developmental environment. The principles and organizational and pedagogical conditions of the formation of environmental competence have been determined.

Keywords: model, competence, structural components of innovative competence, principles of the formation of environmental competence of future teachers and organizational and pedagogical conditions.

In order to make responsible decisions in today's complex environmental conditions, it is important for a person to have not only a deep knowledge of the various spheres of the environment, but also the ability to act in a specific or crisis environmental situation. The process of solving ecological problems determines the need to increase the level of ecological culture of the population. Modern education, which has been modernizing in recent years, is called upon to address this important problem. Its success depends largely on the training of pedagogical staff, and therefore the formation of an environmental culture of teachers and the professional training of students in higher education institutions to solve environmental education problems is becoming increasingly important. Being ecologically competitive is acting skillfully in a given environmental situation based on previous knowledge and experience. Ecological competence is the set of interrelated personal qualities (knowledge, skills, skills, methods of activity) necessary for future teachers to maintain the environment. Ecological competence is the ability, willingness, and experience of an individual to take care of the environment and solve environmental problems. Ecological competence is the ability to apply theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies acquired in the field of ecology to practical and

theoretical problems encountered in everyday life. Ecological competence is Latin for "competent". In addition to purely professional knowledge, skills, and abilities, competence also includes the ability to take initiative, collaborate, work in a group, communicate effectively, evaluate objectively, think logically, and process and use information. Education aimed at the formation of ecological competences is education aimed at the formation of competences in teachers to be able to apply acquired knowledge, skills and competencies in their personal, professional and social activities. [1]

Competence is a characteristic of the new quality of training, which allows to use the acquired knowledge and skills in a non-standard situation at the interdisciplinary level and, most importantly, to achieve subsequent changes and successes on the basis of the acquired knowledge. [7]

Competence - a quality that serves as a criterion for the development of individual intellect, a special type of organization of knowledge in the subject, which implies a high level of understanding of the problem in the relevant field of activity, experience in performing complex actions, reflections and the effectiveness of assessments. [6] Competence - the sum of knowledge, skills and abilities that allow the subject to adapt to changing conditions;

© LA. Lavrentiev, in fact, in 2012, it's his ability to move and survive in certain conditions. They're all about human experience and human activity. Competencies don't come from outside of the situation and the activity. [8]

The term "environmental education" has been interpreted as "environmental education", which became the basis for the definition of education to solve environmental problems associated with the study of the natural sciences-ecology. Ecological competence (specialist) is defined as an object of a complex system based on the combination of theoretical knowledge, practical skills in the field of ecology, and certain personal qualities that perform a specific function in the system of professional activity, which leads to a readiness for environmentally adequate behavior in the context of ethical choice. Ecological competence is the application of knowledge about the environment and human activities, environmental health risks, and the ability to act in an environmentally sound manner under certain living conditions. Today, the most promising strategy for socio-economic development The Concept for Sustainable Development adopted by 179 heads of state and government, including Uzbekistan, emphasizes the need to change people's minds and lifestyles towards measuring needs within the capabilities of natural ecosystems. Ecological competence is the ability, willingness and experience of a person to

solve environmental problems in order to preserve the environment in which they live. The ability to solve ecological problems, experience in practical work on environmental protection and improvement, personal qualities of ecological significance means thrift, responsibility for the results of environmentally oriented activities. The environmental functions of an ecological compliant are: - ecological; - predictive; - social; - cultural; - professional. The initial stage of the formation of an individual's ecological competence is environmental literacy, which is characterized by four components: 1) understanding nature as the habitat of mankind, its "home"; 2) knowledge of natural science about the interaction of nature and society; 3) organizational and other abilities of environmental activity; 4) ability and skills to operate instruments that determine the state of the natural environment. In accordance with the profile of educational institutions providing vocational training, retraining and upgrading of specialists, the teaching of subjects on environmental protection, environmental safety and rational use of nature should be ensured. At the level of higher education institutions, this task can be solved through a wide range of pedagogical tools that do not have a systemic character (ecology of some topics of the model programs, extracurricular activities, excursions), as well as educational activities of museums, libraries, especially protected natural areas, zoos, botanical gardens and others. [5]

The following organizational forms are used in the process of forming ecological competencies of students:

- * public (conferences, olympiads, exhibitions, thematic weeks);
- * group (various forms of classes, presentations, practical exercises, games, excursions);
- * personal (counseling, interviews)

Several stages can be identified in the work on the formation of ecological competencies of students:

- Stage 1 is "learning to know". It's the building of environmental knowledge and skills. This is done through the study of biology, ecology, geography, chemistry courses in higher education. In the upper courses, the formation of ecological competence is carried out through various types of student activities: group preparation for the Olympics with talented students, individual classes.

- Stage 2 is "learning to learn". It's the stage of creating one's own creative products, of doing environmental projects. This is done through individual work

with students. For example, at this stage, the projects "sewage treatment model" and "soil as a habitat" were implemented.

- Stage 3 is "learning to live". At this stage, it is important to actively participate in environmental actions, such as "green hands", "Ecohamyon", "paper" kabi. It's about creating an active life position, educating people who are not indifferent to the problems of life in their region.

- Stage 4 is "learning to be". Regular victories in the city and regional level Olympiads are the result of joint work with students. At this stage, the formation of environmental competence is completed, in which the student chooses a life path and is then automatically implemented in the process of environmental activity.

Examples of activities for the formation of ecological competences in the example of pedagogical practice: The system conducts a lesson on the topic of "the characteristics of ecological groups of plants". It covers the concept of "ecological factors" and their types, the names of plant groups in relation to various factors of inanimate nature such as light, heat, water, and examines relevant examples of plants". Freedom from the slums", in which students act as eco-leaders. The purpose of the lesson is to develop students' responsible attitude towards waste and to take practical steps to solve the problem of waste in everyday life. It introduces the concepts of "natural resources" and "the life cycle of things", and it introduces students to each of the five stages of the life cycle. For students, a recycling report is presented as one of the main ways of solving the waste problem, after which the students suggest options for recycling the waste. The outcome of the lesson is to encourage future teachers to participate in environmental actions, and the homework is to create environmental posters. A creative exhibition "Protecting birds" dedicated to the International Day of Birds and aimed at the protection of birds will be organized in higher education institutions. The exhibition features rare red books, extinct and small species, as well as representatives of the city's flora. During the exhibition, the impact of human activity on the environment is examined. All students who want to participate in the action of the city "green hands", dedicated to the Day of greening the city. The students hand out pre-made leaflets to the city's residents, informing them about the purpose of the action. For every one of these eco-actions, 100 of the city's residents get noticed. All higher education institutions (students and parents, teachers and other employees) participate in the annual "paper" action to collect paper. At the time of writing, over 1,000 kilograms have been collected, saving the trees. The

university periodically holds a seminar entitled "Modern methods of environmental quality assessment". During the seminar, participants conduct small-scale research projects and create model solutions to environmental problems. Students are encouraged to do ecological projects. For example, "identifying air pollution in areas by the sulfate content of tree bark", "studies of noise pollution in the central part of the city", "the effect of urban environment on the climate". Regular work is carried out with students on preparation for the theoretical stage of the Ecology Olympiad. In the process of acquiring ecological competencies, students gradually form an ecological mindset as the basis of ecological culture and ecological maturity, which in turn is an important component of the formation of an intellectual and moral personality. An intelligent, literate, environmentally conscious and highly ethical person is able to understand and assess the global nature of the environmental crisis and take responsibility for his or her actions in nature and the actions of other people. [4]

Competence is the ability of a person to independently apply acquired knowledge and skills in a new situation. In accordance with the meaning of the concept of "safety" included in the Law on Environmental Protection, an environmentally safe activity is understood as a quality that ensures the state of environmental protection, human health, safety of life. Ecological competence and student-led activity - in higher education, such activities include study, communication, social practice and vocational orientation. If this problem is to be solved based on the student's leadership activity and the associated lifestyle and behavior (including the consumption of material and spiritual benefits), the effectiveness of the formation of ecological competencies in students will increase significantly. Leading activities are not only considered as a means of building environmental competence, but also as an object of its application. Environmental competence, based on the leading activities of students, allows the implementation of the basic principles of environmental education in practice: from abstract environmental problems to real, from global environmental problems to local environmental problems of the environment to personal environmental safety.

Based on the above, we propose to highlight the following important areas of environmental competence in general education:

- ecology of educational activities,
- the ecology of communication,
- environmental-oriented educational and social practice and
- the ecological aspect of vocational training.

At different stages of education, these lines of meaning are implemented in different proportions depending on the student's leadership activity. For example, in higher education, educational activities in the field of ecology and related lifestyles and student behavior have created the foundations of environmental competence, but continue to evolve throughout education. Educational ecology is a branch of human ecology that studies the relationship between an individual's educational activities and the educational and social environment that surrounds them. The content of this field of knowledge is:

- evaluation of the impact of environmental conditions on academic success;
- Design and organization of the environment to improve research results, health and safety;
- ensuring environmental safety in working with information flows;
- use general education skills to disseminate ideas;
- social partnership in solving local environmental problems, economic consumption and healthy lifestyles.

Ecological competence in the field of ecology of educational activity implies the ability of the student to design and organize educational activities taking into account the temporary conditions of its implementation; relations between educational subjects; requirements of the state standard and educational program; individual resources of the student; educational burdens and their impact on health and environmental safety, etc. Thus, ecological competence is provided through the implementation of interrelated, common cultural tasks of education, upbringing and development, and includes the formation of:

- knowledge of the natural-scientific and socio-cultural laws of human activity (life) in the environment; activities related to environmental hazards for the environment, human health, safety of life; rules of ecologically safe life;
- the ability to design their activities from the point of view of environmental safety (targeting, predicting consequences, planning, organizing, communicating, assessing risks to environmental safety);
- a responsible attitude to the consequences of its activities for environmental safety, human health and safety.

The main concepts necessary for the formation of ecological competence are: ideas, activities, environmentally safe activities, project, management, performance, resources, compulsory (ecological, legal, moral), environmental risk, environmental damage, environmental monitoring, precaution (ethical

principle), prevention of harm to the environment, health and safety of life. Environmental culture is not a specific type of culture that governs the relationship of humans to the natural world, but rather a vector of all the components of modern human culture. Ecological competencies are all the basic competencies formed in general education as the ability of a student to apply values, ecological thinking and behavior in socially problematic environmental situations that arise in various forms and directions of human activity. [2]

Types of components of ecological competence:

1. Adequate (conscious, active) environmental competence. This type is characterized by a high level of environmental knowledge, skills, concern, and empathy for environmental problems and their consequences, and the formation of an active environmental stance that is manifested in daily environmental practice.

2. Authentic environmental competence. This type is also characterized by the formation of environmental knowledge and skills, participation in environmental activities, but without internal motivation (high level of concern, interest in environmental problems), mainly under pressure from the administration of educational institutions, public opinion, fashion.

3. Inert environmental competence. This type is characterized by a high level of environmental knowledge and skills, sufficient attention to environmental issues, but low activity in implementing environmental practices.

4. Irrational environmental competence is characterized by a high level of concern, in some cases exaggeration of the environmental situation, and active participation in environmental activities with insufficient or no knowledge of the necessary knowledge, environmental problem-solving skills.

Thus, ecological competence as a set of environmental knowledge and beliefs manifested in social practice is inextricably linked to the socio-economic, political, and ideological realities of modern society. [9]

The practical component of ecological competence implies: the ability to apply environmental knowledge in practice in identifying, solving and preventing environmental problems, improving the state of the environment; the availability of practical experience in environmental activities. It implies the existence of value directions, understanding the meaning of environmental activity, the need to protect the natural environment as the most important value; understanding the social and personal significance of environmental activity; confidence in one's participation in the protection of the living environment; conscious civic position; willingness to actively participate in

environmental activities, environmental conditions; responsibility for the results of one's environmental activities, decisions made in the field of environmental change and protection. In the process of studying the subject "Ecology and sustainable development", the formation of students' environmental competencies is based on the most effective scientific principles.

The principle of continuity of the choice of the subject "Ecology and sustainable development" emphasizes the continuity of the acquisition of environmental knowledge by students in the educational process.

The content of ecological education is reflected in the following aspects:

- scientific (development of scientific and educational attitudes to the social environment);
- value (determining the value of nature in society and human life);
- mastery of the system of normative (ethical and legal norms and rules);
- activities (forming scientific, practical and creative skills, types and methods of activities of environmental nature).

-activity - solving environmental problems, conducting environmental research, creating and implementing environmental projects (developing a plan, creating a project, identifying and finding a model, forecasting, applying ICT). [3] The principles of formation of ecological competence of future teachers are defined, which link all components of the educational process into a coherent system, provide the necessary level of formation of ecological competence and are implemented in pedagogical technology. Ecologist N . N. Moiseyev argues that "the leader of the century will not be the country that today has the highest standard of living and the most advanced electronics, but the people who find a relationship with the environment that ensures the transfer of knowledge and culture and meets modern needs". Ecological competence helps future teachers to form an ecological culture, to develop an interest in nature, to convince them of the need to protect the environment, to convey their knowledge about the world's environmental problems to students in an understandable and meaningful way.

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